

DESIGN OF ACOUSTIC HYPERBOLIC METAMATERIALS BASED ON TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATION

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Keywords: Acoustic metamaterial, Hyperbolic dispersion, Topology optimization, Effective medium theory, Negative mass density

ABSTRACT

Topology optimization of a two-dimensional hyperbolic metamaterial is presented in this paper. The optimized metamaterial exhibits hyperbolic dispersions in a broad frequency range. It can support subwavelength imaging with extremely high resolution. We also discuss the mechanics of these exotic wave behaviors.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metamaterials provide many encouraging opportunities to modulate and control wave propagation with the extraordinary physical properties. Hyperbolic metamaterials (HMMs) with hyperbolic dispersions show strong anisotropy. As one of the most important types of metamaterials they have attracted wide attention and showed many promising applications, including negative refraction, enhanced superlensing effects, strong thermal emission, improved absorption and intensified spontaneous emission, etc. The concept of HMMs has been applied to engineering materials for controlling the electromagnetic waves and acoustic waves. Over the past two years, several research groups have focused on the HEMMs and proposed different microstructure topologies. However, the reported HEMMs show the relatively narrow operating frequency range. And the empirical design is unable to overcome the limitation and make the HEMMs more practical. Therefore, a systematic methodology is necessary for design the microstructure topologies exhibiting hyperbolic dispersion in modulating the elastic subwavelength waves.

2 OPTIMIZATION METHOD AND RESULTS

In this paper, mathematical formulation of topology optimization is developed based on the effective medium theory to design a two-dimensional HEMM with hyperbolic dispersion in a broadband region with a given target frequency range ^[1]. The improved single-objective genetic algorithm (GA) is adopted to solve the optimization problem. We consider the design of a square-latticed (lattice constant is $a=0.03$ m) perforated single-phase metal structure made of stainless steel with the mass density $\rho=7850$ kg m⁻³, the Young's modulus $E=200$ GPa and the Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.3$. The orthotropic symmetry of the metamaterial is assumed. By employing topology optimization, we construct some novel microstructure topologies which are difficult to conceive through conventional intuition.

A typical optimized structure is shown in Fig. 1 in the target frequency range of (0.5Hz, 9.5kHz). Fig.2 shows the band structure (Fig.2a), transmission of the longitudinal wave (Fig.2b), effective mass density (Fig.2c) and effective elastic stiffness (Fig.2d) along the two principal directions of a finite HEMM sample. It can be seen that the optimized HEMM exhibits hyperbolic dispersion in a wide frequency region from 4.5 to 9.75kHz and support the subwavelength imaging. We find that mechanism of the hyperbolic dispersion is the multipole resonances in the unitcell.

Fig. 1 Optimized hyperbolic metamaterials in a square lattice (a) and the microstructure topology of the unitcell (b)

Fig. 2 Band structure along the ΓX - and ΓY -directions for the in-plane waves (a), transmission along the two principal directions of a finite HEMM sample for the longitudinal input excitation (b), effective mass density along the x- and y-directions (c) and effective elastic stiffness (d).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 11532001).

REFERENCES

- [1] H.W. Dong, S.D. Zhao, Y.S. Wang and Ch. Zhang, Topology optimization of anisotropic broadband double-negative elastic metamaterials, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, 105, 2017, pp. 54–80 (doi: [10.1016/j.jmps.2017.04.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmps.2017.04.009)).